

Electronic structure and nonlinearity of Schiff bases of furfural and α -amino acids

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Abstract : A series of Schiff bases of furfural (fur) with α -amino acids viz. glycine (gly), alanine (ala), valine (val), phenylalanine (phy), threonine (thr), glutamine (gln), glutamic acid (glu), aspartic acid (asp) and histidine (his) are optimised using RHF/6-31G*. The polarizability and hyperpolarizability are calculated by the finite-field method using AM1 Hamiltonian. It was found that the conformation selectivity of the compounds is due to the side chain in the amino acid. A *trans* conformation along the imino group is stable. The molecules look like a helix with the cavity at the center. The effects of substitution are mainly of steric in nature. The torsion twists of the back bones are characteristic of the substitution. Except fur-phy and fur-his, all the Schiff bases have maximum dipolemoment along the x-axis. The fur-phy and fur-his are found to have dipolemoment maximum along y-axis. The linear, first and second order hyperpolarizabilities follow the dipolemoment order. Schiff bases with acid side chain have very high polarizability and comparable with metal clusters.

Keywords : Nonlinear optical properties, Schiff base, amino acid.

Introduction

Novel nonlinear optical (NLO) materials are of great demand due to the critical role they play in contemporary photonic devices¹. Some excellent NLO materials such as inorganic mineral oxides, KH_2PO_4 , LiNbO_3 , $\beta\text{-BaB}_2\text{O}_4$ and LiB_3O_5 have already been successfully commercialized². During the past two decades, efforts have been extensively devoted to the study of semiconductors, conjugated polymers and organic crystals for NLO properties³. Some of the clusters show considerable third-order NLO properties comparable to or even much stronger than those of C_{60} , which is one of the best molecules reported for optical limiting property⁴. The NLO properties of compounds with different structural types have been discussed by many authors⁵. In recent years, much attention has also been paid in the study of the NLO properties of fullerenes⁶, Schiff base compounds^{7,8} and other organometallic compounds⁹.

In this paper, a series of Schiff base compounds of furfural (fur) and α -amino acids namely glycine (gly), alanine (ala), valine (val), phenylalanine (phy), threonine (thr), glutamine (gln), glutamic acid (glu), aspartic acid (asp) and histidine (his) are modeled to enlight on their

NLO properties. The static polarizability and hyperpolarizability of these simulating models are calculated using the finite-field method¹⁰ and the results are compared and discussed.

Results and discussion

Geometry :

The Schiff bases optimized using RHF/6-31G* level are shown in Fig. 1. The summary of the geometrical parameters is given in Table 1. The interesting feature of the molecular conformation is the observation of an intramolecular hydrogen bond (H-bond) between $\text{O}_5\text{-H}_{18}$ and $\text{N}_7\text{-H}_{18}$. This H-bond results in the formation of two pentagonal ring moieties. The conformation selectivity of the compounds is due to the side chain in the amino acid that results in a *trans* conformation along the imino group. The basic skeleton of the Schiff bases studied is helical. Substituents have negligible effects on the bond lengths and bond angles in general. The bond angle $\text{N}_7\text{-C}_8\text{-C}_9$ has small influence on the substituents and it varies by $\sim 6^\circ$ from fur-gly.

When bond lengths and bond angles are compared, the twist angles have higher influence on substitution.

Fig. 1. Optimised structure of Schiff bases.

The twist angles between furan ring and imino group is about 15° (Table 1). The effect of substituents on the twist angle is of the order : $N_7-C_8-C_9-O_{11} > C_3-C_4-C_6-N_7 \sim C_6-$

$N_7-C_8-C_9$. The molecule looks like a helix with the cavity at the center. Pearson's correlations between the geometrical parameters and molecular weight have negligible

Table 1. Important geometrical parameters of Schiff bases

Schiff base	Bond length (Å)			Bond angle (°)		Dihedral (°)		
	C ₆ -N ₇	O ₁₁ -H ₁₈	N ₇ -C ₈	C ₄ -C ₆ -N ₇	N ₇ -C ₈ -C ₉	C ₃ -C ₄ -C ₆ -N ₇	C ₆ -N ₇ -C ₈ -C ₉	N ₇ -C ₈ -C ₉ -O ₁₁
fur-gly	1.2524	0.9491	1.4508	131.7401	111.0986	164.2753	102.1238	-68.4994
fur-ala	1.2522	0.9494	1.4567	132.1236	108.2107	165.3406	102.0264	-73.9000
fur-val	1.2522	0.9495	1.4565	132.6652	105.9741	168.8208	98.2248	-83.2345
fur-phy	1.2522	0.9496	1.4548	132.2023	107.8192	166.5659	101.2324	-75.8519
fur-thr	1.2525	0.9500	1.4530	132.1417	108.0043	167.0542	106.1114	-73.7981
fur-gln	1.2531	0.9496	1.4564	132.4809	107.6842	168.3452	98.8742	-77.9101
fur-glu	1.2537	0.9498	1.4584	132.4449	107.7475	166.0756	99.0916	-78.4200
fur-asp	1.2555	0.9497	1.4584	132.7213	108.1125	170.6620	95.2885	-80.2571
fur-his	1.2518	0.9497	1.4565	132.0747	107.7941	164.4659	102.7276	-75.9444

correlation except with twist angle N₇-C₈-C₉-O₁₁. Therefore the effect of substitution is mainly of steric in nature. The helical geometry is due to intramolecular H-bond. The back bone structures are stabilized by the intramolecular H-bond. The torsion twists are characteristic of the substitution.

Linear and nonlinear hyperpolarisabilities :

In order to find out the electronic effect, the total Mulliken charge density of C₈ is calculated. This is because of the fact that the side chains are attached to it for all the Schiff bases. The charge density of C₈, HOMO and LUMO and energy gap were calculated using RHF/6-31G* (Table 2). There is no distinct difference among the Schiff bases in the total Mulliken charge density of C₈, HOMO and LUMO. The furan ring is mainly contributed in the HOMO. Therefore the π -bond delocalization in the molecule is in small extent only and the molecules show charge delocalization in the furan ring.

Table 2. Mulliken charge density on C₈, HOMO and LUMO

Schiff base	Charge density (C ₈)	Energy (kcal/mol)	
		HOMO	LUMO
fur-gly	-0.2847	-215.9262	51.5813
fur-ala	-0.15586	-214.9222	52.4598
fur-val	-0.1350	-214.0437	52.4598
fur-phy	-0.1514	-202.1201	52.3343
fur-his	-0.1691	-196.5989	57.9819
fur-thr	-0.1758	-216.6792	49.0085
fur-gln	-0.1608	-218.3101	47.3770
fur-glu	-0.1783	-214.0437	51.3303
fur-asp	-0.1627	-224.9623	37.9016

Based on the side chain the Schiff bases are classified into four groups namely, Group 1 with alkane side chain viz. fur-gly, fur-ala and fur-val, Group 2 with aromatic side chain viz. fur-phy and fur-his, Group 3 with acidic side chain viz. fur-glu and fur-asp and Group 4 with other substituents viz. fur-thr and fur-gln. The results of calculated dipole moments and the first-order hyperpolarizability are given in Table 3.

Except Group 2 Schiff bases all others have higher dipolemoment along the x-axis. The fur-phy and fur-his have dipolemoment maximum along y-axis. Among Group 2, fur-his has higher dipolemoment. This may be due to the presence of aromatic heterocyclic side chain. It is observed that the magnitude of first-order hyperpolarizabilities β_{iii} will roughly follow μ_i , the dipolemoment in the corresponding direction.

The second-order hyperpolarizable components γ_{iiii} , as well as those of linear polarizability α_{ii} , are related to the quantities which are believed to reflect the susceptibility of electronic systems. The calculated values of second-order hyperpolarizability and linear polarizability are given in Table 4. Both of them have similar trend of dipolemoment and first-order hyperpolarizability. The second-order hyperpolarizabilities are comparable with metal clusters¹¹.

In Group 1 the hyperpolarizabilities found is of the order : fur-val > fur-ala > fur-gly. The higher value for fur-val is due to bulky substitution and there by to the loss of symmetry. The order of hyperpolarizabilities among Group 2 is fur-his > fur-phy. The higher value of fur-his is due to aromatic heterocyclic side chain that may cause

Table 3. Dipolemoment (unit : D) and first-order hyperpolarizability (unit : au)

	fur-gly	fur-ala	fur-val	fur-phy	fur-thr	fur-gln	fur-glu	fur-asp	fur-his
μ_x	2.629	2.506	2.1465	0.2979	2.3442	2.1326	1.4768	2.0780	-0.5986
μ_y	-0.306	0.317	1.0194	-2.4305	1.3533	1.1784	0.9742	0.3590	3.1147
μ_z	-0.073	0.568	0.7811	0.1362	0.1843	-0.3314	-1.0691	0.0374	-0.2948
β_{xxx}	1081.038	1727.529	3603.026	50.516	-5527.804	-360.553	-2091029	-41411	-153.383
β_{yyy}	-16.546	-137.694	-30.032	87.830	496.745	-138.481	984074	3763.467	-293.743
β_{zzz}	37.966	-397.132	-374.152	-20.261	74.328	42.885	-17260	195.087	-4.176
$\beta_{x,av}$	821.054	1490.037	2614.387	89.824	-4078.744	-290.710	-1841559	-29023.533	-153.429
$\beta_{y,av}$	-40.440	-616.830	-275.988	36.126	1737.482	-112.535	1718879	11250.968	-162.226
$\beta_{z,av}$	-25.404	-831.583	-1071.421	-134.641	1006.236	165.608	105727	3005.979	-91.438

Table 4. Calculated linear polarizability (unit : au) and second-order hyperpolarizability (unit : au)

	fur-gly	fur-ala	fur-val	fur-phy	fur-thr	fur-gln	fur-glu	fur-asp	fur-his
α_{xx}	126.942	131.542	141.155	131.574	136.627	138.820	-781.179	118.286	138.857
α_{yy}	70.327	65.494	66.735	156.061	60.333	104.326	-221.285	59.148	151.655
α_{zz}	38.164	41.010	77.374	117.872	78.653	85.932	-124.329	73.898	81.067
γ_{xxxx}	-194700	-524581	-1.4×10^6	6237	-2.2×10^6	-48874	Very high	Very high	23123
γ_{yyyy}	13080	-4054	4225	17742	-196668	4348	Very high	-850731	21786
γ_{zzzz}	-1284	-10274	-58377	5932	-21627	13571	5.2×10^7	2106	6166
γ_{xxyy}	13115	-38855	-4394	9966	-317356	-7832	Very high	-3.1×10^6	7954
γ_{xxzz}	9239	-144196	-255142	4459	-97157	16777	7.1×10^7	-300939	8924
γ_{yyzz}	3733	-51253	-328.158	6071	-89910	5038	6.5×10^7	-41201	3532
γ_{av}	-26145	-193309	-401050	14182	-700586	-597	-1.3×10^9	-7.6×10^6	18380

more electron delocalization. In the series of Schiff bases, Group 3 has very high hyperpolarizabilities than all others. Therefore it can be concluded that dicarboxylic acid Schiff bases have more effects on hyperpolarizabilities. Further, fur-gln has higher polarizability than fur-asp which can be attributed to the long side chain in the former.

The polarizability of Group 4 Schiff bases is of the order : fur-thr > fur-gln where hydroxyl group is more effective than amide. In general, the polarizabilities are attributed to the intramolecular hydrogen bonding between the hetero atoms in the molecules similar to photochromic and thermochromic behaviours of Schiff bases¹¹. The overall second-order hyperpolarizability is of the order : fur-glu > fur-asp > fur-thr > fur-val > fur-ala > fur-gly > fur-his > fur-gln > fur-phy. Hence it is concluded that Schiff bases with acidic side chain have more hyperpolarizabilities.

Method :

All the semiempirical calculations were performed using MOPAC program version 6.0¹². The General Atomic and Molecular Electronic Structure System

(GAMESS) program¹³ was employed for the *ab initio* calculations in this study. The 6-31G* basis set¹⁴ was used. The polarizability was calculated by finite-field method using AM1 Hamiltonian at high precision using the key words GNORM = 0.1 and LOCALIZE^{15,16}.

Conclusion :

In this work, nine Schiff bases formed by furfural with α -amino acids viz. gly, ala, val, phy, thr, glu, gln, asp and his are modeled. The Schiff bases have intramolecular hydrogen bonding between hetero atoms. The conformation selectivity of the compounds is due to the side chain in the amino acid. A *trans* conformation along the imino group is formed. Substituents have negligible effects on the bond lengths and bond angles. Dihedral N₇-C₈-C₉-O₁₁ is affected by substitution. The molecule looks like a helix with the cavity at the center. Second-order hyperpolarizabilities and linear polarizabilities have similar trend of dipolemoment and first-order hyperpolarizabilities. Schiff bases with acidic side chain have very high second-order hyperpolarizability.

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